

Small atom doping: A (synergistic) strategy to reduce Sn_{Zn} recombination center concentration in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$?

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Abstract

Kesterite $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_x\text{Se}_{4-x}$ is among the most promising inorganic earth-abundant thin film photovoltaic technologies, although currently, the larger voltage deficit compared to more mature chalcogenide technologies is hampering solar-to-electricity conversion efficiency progress in these materials. Most of the latest reports agree on the CZTSSe defect structure as the main limitation for the open circuit voltage. Small atom doping is suggested as an interesting strategy to reduce the concentration of defects without affecting secondary phase formation. In this study, we explore an innovative approach based on the introduction of LiAlH_4 and its further decomposition during the selenization process of CZTSe precursors, as a pathway for hydrogen and lithium/alkali transient doping. This process shows a strong beneficial influence on the crystal growth and solar cell device performance, especially with a significant improvement in V_{oc} and FF. We demonstrate a reduction of non-radiative recombination, and a remarkable 4-fold increase in the carrier lifetime correlating with the reduction of the V_{oc} deficit below 330 mV. A mechanism on how small atoms (Li and H) interact to reduce the concentration of Sn_{Zn} recombination centers while keeping doping relatively unchanged is

proposed, opening fundamental perspectives for the simple and universal transient doping of thin film chalcogenide compounds.

1. Introduction

Thin film photovoltaic (PV) technologies emerged from the need of achieving truly low-cost modules for energy production that are industrially and economically competitive with non-renewable combustion based energy sources. Mass production of thin film modules would allow for building and product integrated photovoltaics (BIPV and PIPV), identified as the key enabling technologies to make “near Zero energy buildings” and “net Zero Energy districts” more realistic. Currently, the thin film PV technologies which have reached competitive power conversion efficiencies (PCE) beyond 20% are based on $\text{Cu(In,Ga)}\text{S}_x\text{Se}_{2-x}$ (CIGSSe) and CdTe absorber materials.^{[1], [2], [3]} Unfortunately, the aforementioned mature technologies make use of scarce and expensive (In, Ga, Te) or toxic elements (Cd).

Therefore, developing PV technologies based on earth abundant and fully sustainable materials is required. Kesterite $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnS}_x\text{Se}_{4-x}$ (CZTSSe) is currently one of the most promising emerging fully inorganic thin film photovoltaic technologies based exclusively on earth abundant elements thanks to its tunable bandgap (1.0 to 1.5 eV) and high absorption coefficient ($>10^4 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).^{[4]–[6]} Nevertheless, the efficiency of CZTSSe based solar cells has plateaued around 12–13% for as much as 7 years, hindering CZTSSe based devices from becoming industrially and environmentally cost-effective.^{[1], [7]–[11]} It is well-known that the main limiting factor in CZTSSe devices is the large open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) deficit.^{[12], [13]} Short circuit current (J_{sc}) is not considered a critical parameter since it can be greatly enhanced optimizing the optical configuration of the device, resulting in many CZTSSe efficient devices achieving more than 80% of the Shockley-Queisser limit J_{sc} (J_{sc}^{SQ}).^{[7]–[9], [11], [12]} Also, Fill Factor (FF) values for CZTSSe technologies are still below commercially required values.^[7] The main limitation of FF is the high recombination rates, which also limit the V_{oc} . The FF in CZTSSe is also affected by an intrinsic high series resistance associated with thick and resistive $\text{MoS}_x\text{Se}_{2-x}$ layers and secondary phase segregation at the back contact (e.g. $\text{ZnS}_x\text{Se}_{1-x}$), the latter being more relevant for S-rich CZTSSe.^[14]

Several origins for the V_{oc} deficit have been proposed in the literature, which can be mainly ascribed to these three regions of the device: (i) the CZTSSe/CdS interface, (ii) the CZTSSe/Mo interface (i.e. the back-contact), and (iii) the bulk of CZTSSe. While still relevant for CZTSe absorbers, losses at front and back contacts seem to become more relevant for S-rich CZTSSe absorbers. However, it has been identified that for the Se-rich composition the main recombination pathways lies in the depletion region, i.e. in the bulk of the absorber.^{[15]–[19], [14], [20], [21], [22]}

Since the potential of kesterite materials as photovoltaic absorbers was discovered, most of the publications have aimed to suppress the numerous detrimental effects of the proliferating secondary phases, while optimizing carrier concentration by controlling the Cu, Zn, Sn and S/Se chemical potentials, i.e. optimizing the intrinsic doping.^{[23]–[26]} This leads to constraints to the growth conditions, aiming for a compositional region where the impact of secondary phases is low. However, the impact of this optimization on the recombination center concentration was majorly disregarded, resulting in extremely low minority carrier lifetimes of less than 1 ns.^[27] Note that the real Shockley-Read Hall (SRH) lifetime is difficult to determine in CZTSSe due to the effect of carrier trapping/detrapping, which can lead to apparent lifetimes larger than 1 ns.^[27] Comparing CZTSSe minority carrier lifetime with its earth-scarce element parent technology (CuInGaSe_2 , CIGSe) which shows lifetimes of more than 50 ns can explain why the CIGSe technology is already at 23% efficiency while CZTSSe is at 13%.^[2]

Efforts towards identifying the main cause of high non-radiative, i.e. SRH recombination leading to low minority carrier lifetimes have been made in the latter years. The first suggested

deterrent was the Cu-Zn disorder leading to bandgap and electrostatic potential fluctuations enhancing recombination rates.^{[28]–[30], [31]} Therefore, the effect of Cu-Zn disorder on the recombination rates has been thoroughly explored in the latter years and is still a matter of discussion, due to publications with contradictory results. Some reports claim it has no direct impact in the V_{oc} since improvements in electron mobility and lifetime have not always been detected for increasing order parameters.^{[28], [32]} Others argue it is a relevant parameter to be addressed for achieving high efficiencies.^[30] Another strongly suggested bulk origin of the high non-radiative recombination rates are non-passivated grain boundaries and/or the presence of bulk intrinsic recombination centers.^{[33]–[35], [36]–[38]}

Recent advances in the microscopic description of recombination processes have been developed, allowing Kim et al.^[13] to calculate the SRH recombination rates for each point defect present in the CZTSe bulk by using the defect concentrations and carrier capture cross-sections obtained by DFT calculations.^{[13], [39]–[42]} Then, it was identified that the origin of low minority carrier lifetime is essentially related to the presence of Sn-related deep defects, specifically Sn_{Zn} . The presence of this defect would result in sub-nanosecond lifetime values in accordance with the estimated experimental values of hundreds of picoseconds.^{[13], [27], [43]} A satisfactory insight on the role of Cu-Zn disorder based on ab initio calculations was proposed by Chen et al., where they showed that it contributed to increase the concentration of Sn_{Zn} recombination centers.^[44] The mechanism can be summarized as follows: Cu-Zn disorder tends to lower the Fermi Energy (E_F) of CZTSSe during growth. The lowered E_F in turn reduces the formation energy of donor-like defects, i.e. Sn antisites. The increased presence of Sn_{Zn} in disordered CZTSSe leads to increased Urbach tailing as a consequence of the enhanced presence of the $[2Cu_{Zn}+Sn_{Zn}]$ cluster.^{[29], [44]}

Furthermore, a Cu-rich/Zn-poor composition during growth is argued to have the same effects. In contrast, a Zn-rich composition results in an increased E_F .^[44] It is worth mentioning that Cu-rich conditions increase the single phase CZTSe window, justifying why the compositional change from Cu-rich to Cu-poor conditions has been successful.^{[45], [46]} However, Zn-rich compositions during growth are not easy to achieve due to the high stability of ZnSe.^[23] In addition, reducing the Sn concentration in order to prevent Sn antisites is not a viable approach due to secondary phase formation (CuSe and Cu_2Se) which would have a strong detrimental effect in the device properties.^[23] The fact that the hole concentration is high under all compositional conditions (i.e., low E_F) owing to high concentrations of Cu_{Zn} , due to both the poor Zn incorporation during growth and the low formation energy of the defect in all chemical conditions, has also been pointed out in ab initio publications.^[13]

To summarize, the bulk of Se-rich CZTSSe is currently limiting the V_{oc} , especially the short minority carrier lifetime due to the presence of Sn_{Zn} recombination centers. Currently, the main technological challenge lies in the fact that lifetime should be increased without strongly modifying the secondary phase formation and the majority carrier concentration, i.e. without modifying intrinsic doping. Aiming for that, in this work we want to point out the fact that Sn_{Zn} defects present a donor behavior (i.e. the formation energy increases with E_F), thus, the following interplay arises: if the Fermi Energy is too high, the V_{oc} will be limited by the low hole concentration and if it is too low it will be limited by the high recombination center concentration. In consequence, the dependence of both secondary phase formation and defect structure (with E_F position determining both carrier concentration and deep defect concentration, with opposite trends) on the intrinsic doping (i.e. Cu, Zn and Sn chemical potentials) indicate a limitation on the bulk performance of CZTSSe in equilibrium conditions. Hence, in order to overcome the 13% efficiency bar it is necessary to explore out of equilibrium conditions by means of transient extrinsic doping.

In order to circumvent all the aforementioned issues and exploiting the apparently disadvantageous fact that Sn_{Zn} is donor, a transient upward E_F shift (i.e. only during growth) has been suggested as a potential promising strategy to reduce the concentration of Sn antisite

defects, while returning to (or even improving) the desired p-type conductivity after the cooling down of the sample.^[13] This treatment therefore would allow for the decoupling of carrier concentration, determined by Cu-Zn defects (V_{Cu} , Zn_{Cu} and Cu_{Zn}), and lifetime, mainly controlled by Sn deep defects (Sn_{Zn}). Yuan et al. have suggested a similar transient mechanism in order to explain the enhanced p-type conductivity of NaF doped CIGS, which was not possible to explain with traditional doping theory.^[47] Indeed, a permanent upward E_F shift (also increasing E_F during growth, when impurities have increased solubility) doping by means of Ga_{Zn} defect formation has been shown to increase V_{oc} even though hole concentration is reduced.^[48] On the other hand, isovalent In doping has shown to be detrimental for V_{oc} while increasing hole concentration, related to the predominant formation of In_{Sn} instead of In_{Zn} due to the larger atomic size, suggesting that other III-valent atoms like B and Al would be preferentially located at Zn positions, acting as donors.^{[49], [50]} It is possible that, due to the higher solubility of extrinsic dopants at high temperatures, the recombination center concentration is more affected than the carrier concentration, indicating the effects of “partial” transient upward E_F shift.

Achieving a transient upward E_F shift is a technologically challenging task, since it is required to find donor impurities at high temperature, which are able to outgas or become electrically inert at room temperature. Hydrogen is probably the most suitable atom for performing transient upward E_F shift, due to the predicted low formation energy of H_i donor defects in CZTSe and CISE, as has been experimentally shown for CISE.^{[51], [52]} Other small atoms such as Li might have similar effects, although to a lesser extent. In addition, it has been shown that Na is able to migrate in CZTSSe via Cu vacancies at room temperature.^{[53], [54]} Thus, unless strong electrostatic interactions arise (i.e. bonding), atoms smaller than Na could show a similar behavior, allowing them to outgas or accumulate at the grain boundaries during the cooling down step, while their solubility decreases with temperature.

In this sense, controlled hydrogen doping during CZTSSe reactive annealing is not straightforward due to the high stability of H_2 and the high toxicity of $H_2(S,Se)$ or hydrazine in the case of solution based CZTSSe. Interestingly, the former CZTSSe efficiency record of 12.62% was achieved under the effects of H_2S toxic gas.^[8] Additionally, in the past, high-efficiency solution-processed CZTSSe devices were grown from a pure hydrazine solution.^{[9], [55]} In this cases, the presence of H_i during growth cannot be completely discarded either, further supporting the hypothesis of an increased E_F during growth resulting in a better performance of CZTSSe absorber, even if the increase in E_F is slight. The incorporation of H in the CZTS surface coming from Al_2O_3 Atomic Layer Deposition has been shown to improve CZTS device performance, either by grain boundary passivation or by selective surface doping.^[56]

In order to achieve a transient upward E_F shift from the gas phase without the use of highly stable compounds and explosive or toxic hydrogen gases, the use of hydrides is explored. In this work, we focus on the effects of $LiAlH_4$ decomposition during the reactive annealing of Se-pure kesterite, where bulk non-radiative SRH recombination is the main limiting factor to the minority carrier lifetime and thus, the V_{oc} . It is known that this hydride decomposes into its own elemental components at sufficiently high temperatures. In particular, $LiAlH_4$ presents a melting temperature of 125°C, from which it starts decomposing.^[57] Therefore, the presence of elemental Li, Al and H during the reactive annealing is expected above this temperature. On the other hand, the use of small alkali metals has already been reported as beneficial for CZTSSe with effects other than the aforementioned transient E_F upward shift, mainly affecting grain growth and grain boundary conditions, with strong evidence of grain boundary passivation effects.^{[11], [33]–[35], [58]–[60]} In particular, Li has been reported to be the most promising alkali.^{[59], [61]} In fact, recently, addition of lithium bis(tri-fluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (LiTFSI), to solution-processed CZTSSe precursor had reported a new former record efficiency (12.7%) for kesterite-based devices, where mainly interface properties are discussed.^[11] However, the role

of Li in the CZTSSe formation and defect characteristics is not discussed, in this work an insight of the mechanism of small atom doping will be provided.

This work proposes a simple yet effective approach to reduce the recombination center concentration of CZTSe absorbers while keeping the hole concentration high, thus reducing the V_{oc} deficit of the solar cell devices, by implementing the use of $LiAlH_4$ during the growth of the absorber CZTSe. Furthermore, the potential beneficial effect of this hydride is twofold, since at high temperatures allows simultaneously for (i) Li treatment and (ii) hydrogen treatment (upward E_F shift) from a gas phase, without the need of any additional step. This study includes a deep investigation and characterization of the effects of Li and H small atom transient doping on the material and device properties in CZTSe-based solar cells, opening fundamental perspectives for simple transient doping in thin film chalcogenide compounds.

2. Results

2.1. Material Characterization and Photovoltaic Performance

Firstly, a comparison of the effects of $LiAlH_4$ decomposition on the composition (XRF), morphology (SEM) and optoelectronic properties of CZTSe (J-V curves) for the two different thermal annealing profiles, i.e. 1-step and 2-step selenization processes, will be presented. The compositions determined from the XRF measurements shown in **Table S1** does not reveal any significant changes in the cation ratios upon $LiAlH_4$ addition regardless of the thermal profile. There is a consistent loss of Sn with respect to Zn. The $Cu/(Zn+Sn)$ ratio of the samples is around 0.71 after selenization and Zn/Sn ratio is around 1.10, which are typical values for as-grown Cu-poor Zn-rich CZTSe absorbers. However, the Se/cation ratio shown in **Figure S1 b**) is dependent on both hydride mass and the thermal process. While reference samples for both 1-step and 2-step reveal the same ratio, the Se content slightly increases with $LiAlH_4$ mass for 1-step while it decreases for 2-step. Additionally, selenization is more homogeneous for 1-step processes if more hydride mass is added, as evidenced by XRF mapping. The latest could be explained by the formation of the well-known alkali-Se phases that can act as fluxing agents catalyzing selenization and grain growth at the annealing temperatures used in this work.^{[11], [58], [60]}

The enhanced grain size revealed by the SEM cross-section images shown in **Figure 1** for 1-step samples is a clear indication that Li-Se and/or Na-Se phases are present during selenization. The larger grains could imply an improved CZTSe/MoSe₂ contact, avoiding the formation of double-layer CZTSe with lesser presence of voids and cracks at the back-side region of the CZTSe layer (see J-V discussion). This demonstrates that the presence of alkali during reactive annealing allows 1-step processes to achieve appropriate grain growth and morphology with reduced processing time. Nevertheless, intriguingly for 2-step processes the grain size decreases with the hydride mass added during the selenization (**Figure S2**). In this case, a reasonable explanation would be the longer and excessive exposure to alkali-Se phases from the hydride decomposition because of the additional annealing step (additional 30 min). This detrimental effect of excessive alkali-Se phases on the CZTSe grain growth and optoelectronic performance has been previously reported, although a negative impact of an excessive exposure to Al and/or H or the effects of the low pressure step cannot be disregarded.^[60]

Solar cell devices were completed for both sets of samples and in-depth characterizations were performed; the optoelectronic parameters are shown in **Figure S3 a**). The performance of the

Reference - CZTSe

20 mg LiAlH₄ - CZTSe

Figure 1. SEM cross-section images of the 1-step process: reference and 20 mg LiAlH₄ samples are shown. An enhanced grain size is observed, as well as indication of grain coalescence, consequence of a liquid-assisted grain growth mechanism. The improvement in grain morphology and contact homogeneity are regarded as the first indicator of a process improving CZTSe quality.

2-step set decreases with the hydride mass while the 1-step set reveals the opposite trend, showing a remarkable performance improvement. This suggests, as it is well-known, that good optoelectronic performance is restricted to Se-rich samples (avoiding the presence of V_{Se} deep defects), with and good morphology/grain size, only if the Se signal increase is not related to an increased thickness of the resistive MoSe₂ or the presence of other detrimental secondary phases.^[37] However, achieving Se-rich CZTSe and big grains with good morphology alone do not guarantee improved performances for kesterite solar cells.^[62] Therefore, the 1-step samples were thoroughly characterized in order to further elaborate on the impact of the LiAlH₄ treatment on the bulk recombination properties.

Figure S3 b) shows the illuminated J-V curves for 1-step samples treated, indicating a clear improvement on all the optoelectronic parameters. The statistical distribution of the relevant optoelectronic parameters for the 1-step annealed samples with different masses of LiAlH₄ as described in the Experimental Section is presented through **Figure 2**. The nominal relative ratio of the introduced Li and H over the total cation concentration, i.e. $\frac{[Li]}{[Sn]+[Zn]+[Cu]}$ and $\frac{[H]}{[Sn]+[Zn]+[Cu]}$ for 20 mg of LiAlH₄ are 14 and 57 respectively, being the maximum number (if every atom introduced acts as dopant) of supplied Li and H atoms to the system are $3.7 \cdot 10^{20}$ Li and $1.27 \cdot 10^{21}$ H atoms. If only a 10% of the hydrogen atoms act as donor dopants, the effects of the transient upward E_F shift should be observed, according to Ref. [13]. **Figure 3a)** presents the corresponding EQEs, including the reflectance losses of the complete devices. Upon addition of 20 mg of LiAlH₄ the efficiency increases from 6.9% (reference CZTSe) to 8.9% (CZTSe-20mg), achieving an impressive V_{oc} of 469 mV in the first optimization, resulting in a V_{oc} deficit ($V_{oc}^{Def} = V_{oc}^{SQ} - V_{oc}^{Measured}$, where $V_{oc}^{SQ} = 0.928 E_g/q - 0.176$ V) of approximately

330 mV, one of the lowest V_{oc} deficit reported for kesterite devices as shown in **Table 1**. The J_{sc} slightly

Figure 2. Statistics of the optoelectronic parameters for the 1-step selenization samples. Improvement in all optoelectronic parameters is observed.

increases from 27.1 to 27.4 mA/cm². Unfortunately, this is in disagreement with the current calculated from the EQE measurements (26.8 to 30.2 mA/cm²) which shows a more remarkable increase in short-circuit current. Current losses in the devices are related to non-optimized window layer reflection and absorption, implying that further efficiency improvements could be achieved. By using optical simulations, we find that with an anti-reflective coating a maximum current gain of 2.5 mA/cm² could be achieved. By using the more accurate J_{sc} extracted from the EQE and considering the current gain that would be obtained using an antireflective coating (ARC) we approximate the optically optimized current of the cell to be around 32 mA/cm². By taking into consideration the optically optimized current the maximum achievable efficiency of the device is 10.3%. Using optimized window layer conditions has shown that there is a 5 mA/cm² loss due to window layer properties, therefore we postulate the possibility of further increasing the current to 34-35 mA/cm², and a projected efficiency of 11.3%.

Table 1. V_{oc} deficits of the most efficient CZTSSe devices reported.

Reference	E_g	V_{oc}	V_{oc} deficit	Relevant features
This work	1.04	469	330	CZTSe – Sputtering – Transient doping
[9]	1.04	490	310	CZTSe – Sputtering – Pre-Selenization
[48]	1.14	515	380	CZTSSe – Sputtering – Ga ³⁺ incorporation
[8]	1.13	541	345	CZTSSe – Sputtering – H ₂ S anneal
[10]	1.5	730	500	CZTS – Sputtering – Heterojunction heat treatment

[7]	1.13	513	370	CZTSSe – Solution processed – Hydrazine
[11]	1.05	477	330	CZTSSe – Solution processed – LTFSI doping
[63]	1.06	507	310	CZTSSe – Solution processed (Sn ⁴⁺)
[64]	1.07	526	310	CZTSSe – Solution processed (method of 66) (CZTSSe/Al ₂ O ₃ /AZTSSe)
[65]	1.07	540	290	ACZTSSe – Solution processed (method of 66)
[66]	1.11	514	350	CZTSSe – Solution processed – Carbon Framework

Figure 3. a) EQE curves of the 1-step set of samples. Averaged Photoluminescence emission spectra shown on the right. Best sub-cell measurement of each sample is shown. Reflectance losses are included. b) EQE derivative used to extract E_G position and standard deviation from EQE data. c) Urbach Energy extracted from the sub- E_G region of the EQE spectra.

The EQE spectra ratios shown in **Figure S4** at the Supplementary Information suggest both an increased junction quality/reduced depletion region recombination related to an increase in the short-wavelength region collection efficiencies, and an improved collection length in the Quasi-Neutral Region (QNR) related to a monotonic increase in the long-wavelength region with the LiAlH₄ mass. All LiAlH₄ treated samples exhibit an improvement in device performance in the long wavelength region, while at least 10 mg are needed to maximize the improvement in the short wavelength region. In the literature, Li surface selective alloying has been predicted and shown to increase the junction quality by improved band-alignment, morphology and reducing shunt paths and therefore improving J_{sc} and FF.^{[58], [67]} Further studies on the modifications of the process on the CZTSe/CdS interface and the CZTSe surface quality should be performed in order to shed light on the short-wavelength region improvement of CZTSe solar cells. Either the incorporation of H_i or a reduction of Cu_{Zn} antisites at the surface could result in an improved band alignment with the CdS by an improved type inversion before the junction.

In-depth compositional profiles for Cu, Zn, Sn, Se, Mo, Na, Li, Al and H were determined by GDOES (see **Figure 4a**). Al is not detected in either of the samples, probably due to a high formation energy of Al³⁺ defects, related to the fact that no 3⁺ cations are present in the CZTSe matrix, added to the high formation temperature of Al₂Se₃ limiting the role of Al during the CZTSe growth.^[68] Hydrogen detection was not achieved either as GDOES is not a reliable technique for measuring hydrogen traces since the detection threshold is relatively high. Although hydrogen is expected to outgas from the material (similarly to Li and to a lesser extent

Figure 4. a) GDOES signal for Cu, Zn, Sn, Se, Na and Mo in the 20 mg LiAlH₄ sample. Detection of Li, Al and H was also tested resulting in no signal. b) Raman spectra of the 1-step samples, only a reduction of the 250 cm⁻¹ is observed.

Al), the presence of trace concentrations of hydrogen cannot be discarded from GDOES measurements, but as will be discussed in the following sections, the hypothetical hydrogen incorporation cannot be electrically active. Lithium is not detected by the GDOES technique in any of the samples either. No (or very little) lithium incorporation is expected due to the lack of alkali diffusion barrier and the use of SLG substrates, letting the Li-Na exchange mechanism proposed by Yang et al. [69] take place, most likely suppressing Li and Na incorporation in the CZTSe matrix. However, Na signal is observed in the CZTSe layer due to the diffusion of sodium from the soda-lime glass, being most evident in the region between CZTSe and Mo, confirming the tendency of Na to segregate at the interfaces.^[70] Another Na enrichment is present after 30 sec of sputtering and is simultaneous with an increase of Zn and Se and to the reduction of other elements (Sn, Cu). This behavior could be explained by the presence (at least in this portion of the sample) of unreacted ZnSe with small grain size, where sodium is expected to segregate at the grain boundaries.

The values of E_g and E_u extracted from EQE measurements remain unchanged after the LiAlH₄ treatment, and are shown in **Figures 3b) and 3c)** respectively.^{[71], [72]} An unchanged energy band gap is consistent with no Li incorporation. However, similarly to hydrogen and H_i defects, Li is expected to be present in the CZTSe matrix during reactive annealing, preventing Sn_{Zn} by forming Li_{Cu} defects, which slightly increase E_F during growth.^[54] However, Li_{Zn} formation energy has been predicted to decrease for higher E_F , probably having an impact on the maximum E_F during growth.^{[67], [73]}

The Raman spectra shown in **Figure 4b)** reveal a decreased area of the 250 cm⁻¹ peak, associated to the commonly called B-type defect, [2Zn_{Cu}+Zn_{Sn}].^[74] A reduced concentration of the B-type defect is expected by following the reasoning above, probably associated to increased Sn_{Sn} incorporation instead of Sn_{Zn}. However, the reduced presence of Zn_{Cu} defects, also suggested by the reasoning above should imply a reduced area of the peak associated to the A-type defect [Zn_{Cu}+V_{Cu}], which is not observed in the Raman spectra. The fact that the area of this peak remains unchanged can be explained by increased V_{Cu} concentration. The areas related to the A-type and B-type defects are shown in more detail in **Figure S5**.

The Urbach Energy (E_u) is a parameter associated to sub- E_g absorption, generally related to band-tailing phenomena.^[72] In kesterite materials, Urbach tails are related to the [2Cu_{Zn}+Sn_{Zn}] cluster, while Gaussian E_g deviations emerge from partial kesterite to stannite transition (via [Cu_{Zn}+Zn_{Cu}]_I)^[29] and no correlation has been shown with the presence of Sn-related deep

defects. These interpretations are supported by ab initio calculations, where $[2\text{Cu}_{\text{Zn}}+\text{Sn}_{\text{Zn}}]$ are revealed to reduce E_{g} and are suggested to act as electron trapping defects, eventually leading to Urbach-like band tailing.^[44] In the framework of transient E_{F} upward shift and also in our samples, Li and H are expected to outgas from the absorber during the cooling-down after the high temperature step. Sn disorder is not relevant at temperatures below the annealing temperature.^[44] Therefore, we assume Sn atoms remain practically fixed during the cooling down step process, meaning the deep-defect concentration also remains constant. Therefore, we infer a reduced Sn_{Zn} defect density. Additionally, the doped samples show a reduced $[2\text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}+\text{Zn}_{\text{Sn}}]$ and constant $[\text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}+\text{V}_{\text{Cu}}]$ concentration as demonstrated by Raman spectroscopy. Lastly, a constant E_{u} for all LiAlH_4 doped samples extracted from EQE is observed (and therefore constant concentration of $[2\text{Cu}_{\text{Zn}}+\text{Sn}_{\text{Zn}}]$). The modification on the concentration of these defects necessarily implies a slight reduction of $[\text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}]$ and an increase of both $[\text{Cu}_{\text{Zn}}]$ and $[\text{V}_{\text{Cu}}]$, which should increase overall p-type doping. This is consistent with predictions of a decreased concentration of donor defects (Zn_{Cu}) and an increased concentration of acceptor defects (Cu_{Zn} and V_{Cu}).^[13] Naturally, the formation energy of neutral defect clusters is not strongly affected by slight modifications of E_{F} , consistent with DFT calculations^[44], being $[2\text{Zn}_{\text{Cu}}+\text{Zn}_{\text{Sn}}]$ an exception due to reaction kinetics not allowing Zn_{Sn} to be formed. This leads to the thinking that the shallow defect structure of CZTSe is slightly affected by the transient upward E_{F} shift. The effects are reduced as compared to Sn defects due to the decreased solubility of Li and H at the moment that Cu and Zn cations become practically fixed due to diffusion mitigation consequence of low temperature.

2.2. Electrical characterization

Dark J-V curves shown in **Figure S6** were analyzed by performing a fitting using the single diode model, allowing to extract the diode quality factor (n), series resistance (R_{s}), shunt resistance (R_{sh}) and reverse saturation current (J_0). The parameters for the best sub-cells of both the reference and the CZTSe-20mg sample are displayed in **Table 2**. It is straightforward that the improvement in the FF is directly related to the changes in both n and R_{sh} . The first parameter is slightly decreased while R_{sh} exhibits a four-fold increase. We attribute the increase in R_{sh} to the increase in grain growth, leading to an increased CZTSe/selective-contact area and therefore less shunting paths. Non-radiative recombination at the SCR is limiting the V_{oc} in CZTSe solar cells, as mentioned in previous sections. The reduction of n indicates an increased recombination rate within the bulk compared to the SCR, where $p \gg \Delta n$ implies a lower non-radiative recombination rates.^[75] Additionally, LiAlH_4 treatment implies a reduction by an order of magnitude of J_0 . The latter strongly suggests decreased recombination rates.^[76]

Table 2. Optoelectronic parameters of CZTSe best sub-cells. Parameters are obtained by Illuminated J-V, Dark J-V, EQE, PL and C-V.

Sample	V_{oc} (mV)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	R_{s} (Ohm.cm ²)	R_{sh} (Ohm.cm ²)	n	J_0 (mA/cm ²)	E_{g} (eV)	E_{u} (meV)	W_{SCR} (nm)	$\tau_{\text{e-}}$ (ps)
Ref	418	27.1	61.3	6.9	0.1	246	1.6	$8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1.03	22	200	60
20 mg	469	27.4	68.9	8.9	0.1	1028	1.4	$6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.04	22	80	260

To support the electrical characterization results, photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) was measured on the devices. While non-radiative losses can be estimated directly from the PLQY by $kT \cdot \ln(\text{PLQY})$, the Quasi-Fermi Level Splitting (QFLS) can be estimated from fitting the high energy slope of the absolute luminescence spectra.^{[77], [78]} Both PLQY and QFLS are shown in **Figure 5a**). It can be seen that the non-radiative losses significantly decrease with

Figure 5. a) QFLS and Non-Radiative losses extracted from PL. Notice the decrease in non-radiative losses upon $LiAlH_4$ introduction while QFLS follows the V_{oc} of the devices. b) Carrier concentration as a function of the average distance from the junction extracted from C-V sweep at 92 kHz and 300K.

increasing hydride mass, while the QFLS increase accordingly and shows the same trend as the measured V_{oc} . The fact that the QFLS values increase with hydride doping and are 10-30 meV larger than the measured V_{oc} is further confirmation that the bulk electronic properties of the devices are improved. Although measurements on bare absorbers showed lower PLQY signals we believe this can be attributed to surface degradation and/or the importance of the heterojunction soft thermal treatment.

An increase in the QFLS may be caused by either a reduced recombination activity and thus a quasi-Fermi level for minority carriers closer to the (conduction) band or a higher doping level and thus a majority carrier quasi Fermi level closer to the (valence) band.

In order to extract the majority carrier concentration, capacitance-voltage profiles were measured at room temperature and 92kHz. The extracted carrier concentrations are shown in **Figure 5b)** for the different films. The carrier densities for all of the measured samples stay within the same order of magnitude, however, a monotonic increase in the carrier concentration (from $\sim 1.5 \cdot 10^{16} cm^{-3}$ to $\sim 6.5 \cdot 10^{16} cm^{-3}$) estimated from the minimum of the CV profile is observed and is partially responsible for the QFLS improvement with $LiAlH_4$ doping. The hole concentration increase, as discussed above, is justified by a slight modification in the shallow defect concentration (Cu_{Zn} , Zn_{Cu} and V_{Cu}). The incorporation of ionized donor H_i point defects would result in an opposite impact in hole concentration, suggesting that H is not incorporated in CZTSe bulk. Anyways, as mentioned previously, trace concentrations located at the grain boundaries or surface cannot be discarded. Nevertheless, a reduction of the SCR width implies a reduced region where the Shockley-Read-Hall mechanism shows higher recombination rates.

However, the change in the SCR width is not strong enough to increase the collection efficiency of electrons generated by long-wavelength photons, in fact it should be detrimental for it, the possible origins for the increase in current and long-wavelength photon collection will be discussed in the following sections.

The minority carrier lifetime can be estimated from the PLQY and carrier density measurements as published previously.^[79] An increased lifetime is expected if the recombination center concentration is reduced. The estimated lifetimes of the reference and the 20 mg samples are

shown in the **Table 1**. We observe a remarkable increase on the minority carrier lifetime, from about 60 ps to 260 ps, resulting in a 4-fold increase compared to the reference sample.

The increased minority carrier lifetime is consistent with both the reduced space-charge region recombination, indicated by a decreased diode ideality factor, and the increased V_{oc} . These observations are consistent with the hypothesis of reduced non-radiative recombination due to a lower Sn_{Zn} concentration.

Unfortunately, the lifetime values are still far away from values that would be required for commercial application of this technology (≈ 100 ns). Nevertheless, the lifetime increase is unequivocally related to a reduction of the recombination rates, regardless of their chemical origin. Therefore, the synthesis method is not hard to implement and should be tested in different precursor configurations, since it should yield similar effects with no dependence with the precursor configuration unless the method finds a limitation.

3. Discussion

To shed light on the effects of reduced $[Sn_{Zn}]$ recombination center 1D numerical analysis has been performed with SCAPS-1D software. In order to understand how the changes in the recombination center concentration and the majority carrier (hole) concentration affect the photovoltaic performance of the CZTSe material in the Mo/CZTSe/CdS/i-ZnO/ITO device configuration both parameters are modified. Details regarding the baseline structure parameters considered are given in the supplementary information **Table S2**.

Figure 6. SCAPS-1D numerically calculated J-V curves. Black and blue color indicate the parametrized material properties implemented (Reference $\rightarrow N_A=1.5 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\tau_e=60 \text{ ps}$ and 20 mg $\rightarrow N_A=6.5 \cdot 10^{16}$ and $\tau_e=260 \text{ ps}$). According to the calculated curves, the increase in hole concentration should dominate the effect on the J_{sc} over the lifetime increase, and therefore current should decrease. Since this is in disagreement with experimental observation, we propose an increased electron mobility (With values $\mu_e=20, 30$ and $40 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V} \cdot \text{s}$, for the dotted, dashed and solid lines respectively) to reproduce the increase in current, as discussed in the text.

To parametrize deep defect recombination, and thus the increase of lifetime, a bulk defect with the properties of Sn_{Zn} has been included, as shown in **Table S3**. The concentration of the defect is adjusted in order to fit the lifetime obtained (60 and 260 ps respectively). This method overestimates the recombination rate, since the experimental measures are able to access the

electron lifetime for the minority carriers in the full-device configuration, and thus take into account recombination losses at interfaces and window layer. Furthermore, the discrepancy between experimental and calculated JV curves is limited as bulk (and specifically Sn_{Zn}) recombination dominates a large part of the recombination rates. However, the effects of the changes in lifetime and hole concentration parametrized in SCAPS-1D should be only discussed qualitatively. Hence, the shallow acceptor doping and the lifetime are simultaneously increased according to the measured values (Reference $\rightarrow N_{\text{A}}=1.5 \cdot 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\tau_{\text{e}}=60 \text{ ps}$ and $20 \text{ mg} \rightarrow N_{\text{A}}=6.5 \cdot 10^{16}$ and $\tau_{\text{e}}=260 \text{ ps}$) to verify if the improvements in the photovoltaic performance can be solely ascribed to these two parameters. As shown in **Figure 6**, it is clear that the improvement of V_{oc} is correlated to the increase of these two parameters. Additionally, the increased FF correlates with the V_{oc} and is marginally affected when increasing the R_{sh} . Surprisingly, the experimentally observed increase in J_{sc} is not reproduced by the calculated curves, i.e. the increase in the lifetime does not compensate the reduction in current due to the increased hole density and reduced SCR width (**Table 2**). We hypothesize that a higher electron mobility (also shown in **Figure 6**) suffices to explain the increase in J_{sc} . While no experimental proof is provided here, the larger grain size could lead to reduced grain boundary scattering and therefore an improved mobility. Additionally, the presence of alkali metals at the grain boundaries can lead to a hole reflector and electron attracter behavior, which effect might be more noticeable in very low injection conditions, explaining the difference in behavior in the EQE only for the LiAlH_4 treated samples.^[33] This hypothesis leads to a possible additional benefit of the presence of small atoms during the CZTSe formation and growth by passivating non-benign grain boundaries, which in some CZTSe absorbers (with low carrier concentration) can dominate the recombination rates.

Lastly, we propose a model of the interaction of small atoms (H and Li) during growth in the framework of defect chemistry. Therefore, we first describe the reaction process of un-doped CZTSe. Due to the high stability of ZnSe, Zn incorporation is delayed as compared to Cu and Sn, as described in **Figure 7**. Therefore, the CZTSe film is Zn poor during the first stages of the reactive annealing. Additionally, Cu and Sn can be present in a 2+ oxidation state. Consequently, Zn vacancies are less stable in CZTSe as compared to cation antisites (i.e. Zn vacancies always show a higher formation energy than Cu_{Zn} and Sn_{Zn}), explaining the proliferation of Cu_{Zn} and Sn_{Zn} defects, as described in **Figure 7 (top)**.^[45] By the end of the high temperature step, all Zn has been incorporated. However, Cu and Sn atoms remain at Zn positions, while Zn atoms occupy Cu and Sn sites.

In the case of small atom-doped CZTSe, a reduction in Sn_{Zn} concentration can be explained by the presence of Li_{Cu} , Li_{Zn} and H_i . As described in **Figure 7 (bottom)**, at the first stages of the reaction, when a small amount of LiAlH_4 has been decomposed, the contribution of H_i to E_{F} upward shift can be expected. Therefore, Li would incorporate at Cu positions, forming Li_{Cu} and also increasing E_{F} if a Cu vacancy is occupied. Thus, during the first stages of the high temperature step (CZTSe formation) the Fermi Energy of small atom-doped CZTSe is expected to be upwardly shifted. As E_{F} keeps increasing, more Li will occupy Zn positions, forming acceptor Li_{Zn} (also Cu_{Zn} will be formed), decreasing the already reduced (due to H_i) probability of Sn_{Zn} formation. Since both Cu and Zn positions are occupied by Li (Li_{Zn} and Cu_{Zn} presenting a lowered formation energy due to the shift of E_{F} and their acceptor behavior), more Sn is sterically bound at Sn positions (Sn_{Sn}), reducing the recombination center concentration. In this case, Zn is able to substitute Li atoms and incorporate at the CZTSe matrix at the Zn positions, reducing the density of Zn antisites. Finally, as the temperature lowers, H and Li solubility decrease and are forced to outgas the material or accumulate at the grain boundaries in very little quantities.

Figure 7. Schematics of CZTSe defect structure during reactive annealing. As mentioned in the body of the text, the starting point is a Zn-deficient CZTSe, due to the high ZnSe stability. This results in a V_{Zn} -rich structure, which is unstable upon the formation of Cu_{Zn} and Sn_{Zn} . The system's energy will be minimized if Zn vacancies are occupied. **Top)** Process for un-doped CZTSe. **Bottom)** Process for small atom doped CZTSe.

4. Conclusion

In this work, the $LiAlH_4$ decomposition during the CZTSe selenization process has been thoroughly investigated. Only short processes have improved the efficiency of the devices, suggesting that the overexposure to the hydride decomposition might be detrimental. Since an incorporation of Li, Al and H in the final film could not be detected, it is believed that these atoms provide CZTSe a transient treatment. On the 1-step processes, an increased selenization rate and grain growth are observed, ascribed to the formation of alkali-Se fluxing phases. In this case, the efficiency of the devices is boosted by more than 2% in absolute and is mostly related to increases in both V_{oc} and FF. The electrical characterization shows a reduced diode ideality factor and J_0 while the series resistance remains constant, indicating a reduction in non-

radiative recombination further supported by a minority carrier lifetime increase by an order of magnitude. C-V profiling reveals an increased carrier concentration. The complementary drift-diffusion numerical analysis shows that an increased carrier concentration and decreased bulk recombination leads to increased V_{oc} and decreased J_{sc} , which indicates a likely additional increase in the electron mobility in order to explain the observed increased J_{sc} . A detailed model of the CZTSe formation and growth from a defect chemistry approach is presented to explain the reduction of CZTSe recombination center concentration (Sn_{Zn}) and the increase in carrier concentration (V_{Cu} , Cu_{Zn} and Zn_{Cu}), consistent with unchanged E_g and E_u values and consistent with the Raman analysis.

In summary, the use of $LiAlH_4$ during the reactive annealing reveals a simple and promising pathway to further improve the CZTSe efficiency due to its ability to address several of the main CZTSe limiting factors at once, being bulk recombination the most relevant one. A clear beneficial impact on the selenization rate, grain growth (and therefore contact homogeneity), majority carrier concentration and front contact has been demonstrated. Further optimization and understanding of the process might enable greatly improved performance of the CZTSe based solar cell devices. The effects of small atom transient doping seem to indicate that an upwardly shifted E_F during growth is an effective method to improve the CZTSe bulk properties for photovoltaic applications owing to its ability to modify the defect structure without affecting the secondary phase formation.

5. Experimental Section

Sample Preparation

Samples were prepared on Mo-coated (DC magnetron sputtering, Alliance AC450) soda-lime glass substrates (SLG). Standard Cu/Sn/Cu/Zn metallic precursor stack was sequentially deposited on top of a Mo tri-layer by DC sputtering. Back contact optimization and structure is explained in Ref. [80]. The precursor composition and thickness was calibrated and measured by X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF, Fischerscope XDV), precursors with Cu/(Sn+Zn)~0.70 and Zn/Sn~1.05 ratios were used. The as-deposited stack was subjected to reactive annealing under Se+Sn atmosphere (100 mg of Se (Alfa-Aesar powder, 200 mesh, 99.999%) and 5 mg of Sn (Alfa-Aesar powder, 100 mesh, 99.995%)) and different masses of LiAlH₄ (Sigma-Aldrich powder, reagent, 95.0%) (0, 5, 10 and 20 mg). The process was repeated for different thermal profiles using graphite boxes (69 cm³ in volume) in a conventional tubular furnace, as shown in **Figure S1 a**) and described below:

1. One step: dwelling time of 15 min with a ramp of 20 °C/min and temperature of 550 °C under Ar static pressure (950 mbar)
2. Two steps: first step with dwelling time of 30 min with a ramp of 20 °C/min and temperature of 400 °C at 1.5 mbar (Ar flux), and second step with dwelling time 15 min with a ramp of 20 °C/min and temperature of 550 °C under Ar static pressure (1 bar)

Solar cell devices were fabricated by depositing 50 nm CdS by chemical bath deposition (CBD) preceded by several chemical etchings in order to remove secondary phases on the surface of the absorber and to passivate it, followed by deposition of 50 nm i-ZnO and 200 nm ITO by DC-pulsed sputtering (Alliance CT100).^{[24], [25], [81]} To perform the optoelectronic characterization, 3 x 3 mm² sub-cells were mechanically scribed using a manual microdiamond scribe (OEG Optical Metrology MR200). Neither antireflective coating nor metallic grids were used for the optoelectronic characterization of the devices. Air hotplate annealing was performed on the full devices for 25 min at 250 °C, including the heating ramp from room temperature.

Device and Material Characterization

Dark and illuminated J – V curves were measured using a calibrated Sun 3000 class AAA solar simulator (Abet Technologies, 25 °C, AM1.5G illumination) under ambient conditions. The spectral response was measured using a Bentham PVE300 system calibrated with Si and Ge photodiodes in order to obtain the external quantum efficiency (EQE) of the solar cells. Reflectance was measured using a built in integrating sphere accessory in the spectral response equipment. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were recorded on a ZEISS Series Auriga microscope utilizing electron beam with 5 kV accelerating voltage. Room temperature capacitance voltage measurements (CV) were carried out using an impedance analyzer from Novocontrol Technologies. A parallel circuit model was assumed to derive the device capacitance. From CV measurements, doping profiles were calculated using the formalism of Miller and a relative dielectric permittivity of $\epsilon = 8.5$ for CZTSe.^[82]

Glow Discharge Optical Emission Spectroscopy (GDOES): A depth profiling analysis of composition on some selected samples was performed by GDOES measurements using a Horiba Jobin Yvon GD Profiler 2 spectrometer, equipped with an anode diameter of 4 mm and 19 element channels.

Photoluminescence (PL): Absolute photon number calibrated CZTSe photoluminescence spectra were obtained with 660 nm excitation under AM1.5-equivalent illumination intensity. Hyperspectral luminescence images were obtained using a peltier-cooled InGaAs-Camera

together with a liquid crystal tunable band pass filter. The system was calibrated for absolute photon counts using an integrating sphere and a calibrated halogen light source.

Raman spectroscopy: Raman spectra were obtained using micro-Raman (Renishaw's inVia Qontor) microscope. Excitation wavelength was 532 nm with a nominal incident power of 1 mW and a spot size of 0.25 μm . Nine spectra were obtained at different surface points for each sample, normalized averages are presented in the body of the text. The position of all spectra has been corrected by taking into account the first order Raman spectrum of monocrystalline silicon as a reference measured before each acquisition and imposing its position at 520 cm^{-1} .

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Table of Contents

Due to the strong detrimental effects and the complexity of secondary phases in the Cu-Zn-Sn-Se system, the changes on the defect structure of kesterite absorbers with different treatments have been disregarded. In this work, small atom doping is explored as a pathway to engineer the defect structure of kesterite materials leading to significant efficiency improvements without a clear modification on the secondary phase formation.

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Small atom doping: A (synergistic) strategy to reduce SnZn recombination center concentration in $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSnSe}_4$?

